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Research Article

**OCCURRENCE OF EAR, NOSE AND THROAT (ENT)
SURGERY EVIDENCE IN HIV-POSITIVE PATIENTS IN
PUNJAB PROVINCE PAKISTAN**¹Dr. Sana Mushtaq, ²Mohammad Jalil, ³Dr Yumna Sarmad¹Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore, ²Baqai Medical University Karachi, ³Sheikh Zayed Medical College Rahim Yar Khan.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To this day, HIV/AIDS remains a 21st century threat. The overall pace of new HIV infections are steadily decreasing in some countries, but there is still a burden of disease in Asia. A few surveys have shown that 73 to 95 percent of the Patients infected with HIV have manifestations in the ears, nose and throat. The purpose of this survey was to Recognize the extent of ENT signs in HIV-infected patients. at KCMC based on age, gender and CD4 counts.

Methods: It is an illustrative cross sectional examination directed to the KCMC clinic including HIV infected patients who visited HIV treatment centers. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. Advantageous tests were used to obtain study members, and 200 patients were recruited. in the exam. Information was collected through a patient survey, and the results were being investigated using SPSS restitution 24.

Results: Sixty-eight (38%) of the 200 HIV-infected patients had ENT indications. The most The age group influenced was 0 to 9 years of age. The onset of ENT was more common in women. (23.5%) than in men (10.5%). Those with CD4 cells check under 200cells/ μ L in addition it was a strong ubiquity (56.3%).

Conclusion: This survey showed that 33% of the population under consideration presented ENT signs. All clinical experts should be aware of the ENT signs in HIV-infected people. to ensure early and appropriate mediation.

Keywords: Ear, Nose and Throat, Surgery Evidence, HIV-Positive, Punjab Province.

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INTRODUCTION:

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) is a retrovirus that infects cells of the resistant frame weakening their capacity and causing the safe to disintegrate frame [1]. The infection contaminates and damages the helper T-cells, debilitates both also, humoral resistance, and extends weakness to embodied life forms such as such as Streptococcus pneumonia and other microscopic organisms [2]. The decimation of the two cells in addition, humoral resistance causes a person to create an acquired immunodeficiency syndrome. condition (AIDS) with ear, nose and throat (ENT) appearance [3]. The ENT signs usually reported in HIV-positive patients incorporate; the candidiasis, extension of the lymphatic center, rhino sinusitis, hypersensitive rhinitis, lymphatic center extension in the neck, amplification of adenoids and constant supportive otitis media. Several surveys have shown that 70 to 90 percent of HIV patients will experience side effects in the ears, nose, and throat [4]. The purpose of our exploration was therefore to distinguish the predominance of ENT indications among clients who visit KCMC HIV centers. Awareness of the pervasiveness of this phenomenon will raise doubts among doctors and medical providers who urge patients presenting to emergency departments with ENT side effects to be tested for HIV. In addition, knowing how HIV clinical markers are usually used in relation to ENT indications will make it possible to design ENT screening plans for clients of HIV centers [5].

METHODOLOGY:

This survey was conducted at the Kilimanjaro Christian Medical Center, a specialized clinic in Kilimanjaro, northern Pakistan, which serves a population of approximately 8,505,809. It is the main emergency clinic with an ENT division in the area. Our current research was conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore from March 2019 to February 2020. Despite the ENT facility, the clinic has three HIV facilities, namely the Care and Treatment Clinic, the Child Centered Family Care Clinic (CCFCC), and the Infectious Disease Clinic, which also served as the setting for this study. All HIV-positive patients, adults and children, who visited one of the HIV centers or the ENT center were selected and invited to participate in the study. We included all HIV-positive patients who visited one of the centers and the ENT center during the review period. The main findings were adenoid hypertrophy, hypersensitive rhinitis, cervical lymphadenopathy, CSOM, laryngitis, esophageal candidiasis, oral candidiasis, otitis externa, rhino sinusitis, sensorineural hearing loss and tonsillitis, with free factors being age, sex and CD4 count. Potential study members in HIV centers were matched by an analyst and agreed to participate in the survey. A pre-tested survey was used to learn about the patient segment and medical history. A headlamp and otoscope were then used by the scientist to examine the patient's ears, nose and throat to try to recognize any ENT conditions, a fiber optic nasolaryngo scope was used in the ENT facility to inspect patients we suspected had nasopharyngeal tumors or a history of nasal death. The findings of the evaluation were recorded along with the segment and clinical history.

Figure 1:

RESULTS:

240 HIV-positive patients who visited the KCMC clinic between February and July 2018 focused on deciding the size and appropriation of ENT signs by age, gender, and CD4 count. All patients were then selected for profoundly dynamic antiretroviral therapy (HAART) in this survey. Their age increased from 6 to 79 years (mean age 42 years). The proportion of Lion members was 139 women (68.6%). The segment qualities of the members are shown in (Table 1). Rhino sinusitis was the best known clinical indication, present in 15 (26%) of the 69 patients who introduced

with ENT appearances. The dispersion of other ENT clinical indications can be summarized as follows During the course of the survey, 69 (37%) patients out of 200 with ENT appearances. Most of the cases have been the gathering of the 40-49 year olds, but in terms of the scope inside age groupings, the most notable ranges were in age clusters 0-9 years (half), and 14 over 50-59 years (47.3%). Table 2 shows the ENT indications we found in the The frequency of occurrence of ENT in women was higher (24.6%) than that of men (12.6%). This distinction was not actually huge anyway (Table 3).

Table 1:

Age (Years)	Presence of ENT Manifestations	N (%)
0-9	Yes	3 (50)
	No	3 (50)
10-19	Yes	9 (28.1)
	No	23 (71.9)
20-29	Yes	6 (23.1)
	No	20 (76.9)
30-39	Yes	11 (36.7)
	No	19 (63.3)
40-49	Yes	20 (35.7)
	No	36 (64.3)
50-59	Yes	14 (45.2)
	No	17 (54.8)
≥60	Yes	5 (26.3)
	No	14 (73.7)

Table 2:

		ENT Manifestation		Total
		Yes	No	
Sex	Male	21	44	65
	Female	47	88	135
		68	132	200

Notes: Chi square, 0.12; P-value, 0.73.

Table 3:

Characteristics	N(%)
Sex	
Male	65(32.5)
Female	135(67.5)
Age (Years)	
0-9	6(3)
10-19	32(16)
20-29	26(13)
30-39	30(15)
40-49	56(28)
50-59	31(15.5)
≥ 60	19(9.5)

DISCUSSION:

The prevalence of ENT signs among the 240 HIV-positive members we selected in our survey was 39%,

which is virtually identical to a test performed at Muhimbili National Hospital by Swai, which reported a 35.3% commonality [6]. We assume that this

distinction is due to the distinction of example size because Jafri's study had an example size of 97. A recent report in India, with an example size of 969 HIV-positive patients, revealed a 77% ubiquity for ENT manifestations.⁴ At the time of the study in India, not all patients were on HAART, making it likely that they had lower CD4 controls than our patients, and hence had a higher incidence rate [7]. Our finding that patients with lower CD4 counts have more ENT indications supports this theory. In this review, 4 (55%) patients aged 0 to 9 years showed greater ubiquity of ENT signs and 6 (24.2%) relatively old patients aged 23 to 31 years were the least likely to have ENT indications. In correlation, a review conducted at the Muhimbili National Medical Clinic revealed that the most invasive age group was 20-29 years of age in 12 (half) of the patients, while the least frequent group was 50-59 years of age with 7 (26.2%) patients [8]. Our survey did not find an evidence-based relationship between gender and ENT indications, while the number of women who protested against ENT was higher. This contradicts a survey conducted at Muhimbili National Hospital where the prevalence of ENT indications was higher among men 36.8% than among women 36.4%; this was in any case not measurably significant. In Iran, it was also found that ENT indications were higher among men than women, but this was also not evidence-based. The empowerment of women in our examination area and the greater well-being of men seeking different conduct from that of women may have contributed to the rise in the number of women in our examination [9]. We found that ENT appearances decreased as CD4 controls developed. Sway in Muhimbili, Pakistan found a comparative model. It is conceivable that as an individual's CD4 control declines and he or she becomes more prone to pioneer diseases, the possibility of creating ENT signs as a component of shrewd infections rises. Some ENT conditions are perceived as entrepreneurial diseases in HIV and have been used in the WHO HIV clinical organization [10].

CONCLUSION:

Of the 240 HIV-positive patients we analyzed, 37% had ENT appearances. In any case, these were not their initial complaints and they were revealed through our testing. We found that as CD4 counts decreased,

patients showed more ENT signs. We therefore suggest that all clients seeking treatment in HIV centers, especially those with CD4 counts below 500 cells/ μ L, should have an ENT examination.

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